

Spectral, Magnetic and Antibacterial Studies of some newly synthesised Manganese (II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes

V. S. SHRIVASTAVA*, C. P. BHASIN and G. C. SAXENA

Chemical Research Laboratories, R. B. S. College Campus, Agra University, Agra-202 004

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Some octahedral Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of the Schiff base derived from 2-furylglyoxal and 2-aminopyridine have been synthesised, characterised and screened for antibacterial activity against a number of microorganisms and have exhibited potential activity. The complexes possess the general formula on the basis of analysis and molar conductance, $[M(L)_2Cl_2]$, where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, L = 2-furylglyoxal 2-aminopyridine. The geometries of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of magnetic and electronic spectral data.

SCHIFF bases have received renewed attention in recent years because of their proven antitumour and carcinostatic activities¹⁻⁴. A number of papers dealing with the studies of metal complexes of the Schiff bases derived from heterocyclic glyoxalic aldehydes with various aromatic amines have appeared in the literature^{5,6}. Hence an attempt has been made to prepare and characterise Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with Schiff base derived from 2-furylglyoxal and 2-aminopyridine.

Experimental

Preparation of the Schiff base: 2-Acetylfuran and its glyoxal were prepared according to the reported procedure^{7,8}. Schiff base has been prepared by refluxing (~3 h) 2-furylglyoxal (1.24 g, 10 mmol) and 2-aminopyridine (0.94 g, 10 mmol) in ethanol. The Schiff base (m.p. 110°) thus obtained was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum.

Synthesis of metal chelates: An identical procedure was adopted for the synthesis of all the metal chelates reported. For the sake of brevity only one reaction has been discussed in detail.

Bis(2-furylglyoxal-2-aminopyridine)-Mn^{II} chloride: To an ethanolic solution of MnCl₂·4H₂O (1.98 g, 10 mmol) was added an ethanolic solution of Schiff base (4.0 g, 20 mmol). The reaction mixture (~50 ml) was refluxed for ~4 h and reduced to one-third of its volume. On cooling, dark red crystals were obtained and recrystallised from 95% ethanol.

Physical measurements: The molar conductances of the complexes were measured in dimethylformamide with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using a dip type conductivity cell having a cell constant 0.5 cm⁻¹.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature. Molar susceptibilities were corrected for paramagnetism of the constituent elements using Pascal's constants.

The IR spectra (KBr) of the ligand and its chelates were recorded in the range 4000–200 cm⁻¹ on a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes in acetone and DMF were recorded using a Pye Unicam SP8-100 spectrophotometer.

Antibacterial screening: All the compounds were tested in DMF by the disc-diffusion technique at S. M. S. Medical College, Jaipur. A disc of 5 mm diameter was used for the control.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of metal chlorides and Schiff base ligand (C₁₁H₈O₂N₂) may be depicted as

where, M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}.

The analytical results indicate a 1:2 (M:L) stoichiometry for all the complexes. The complexes are soluble in DMSO, acetone and dimethylformamide. The molar conductance values (Table I) of 0.001 M solutions of the complexes in DMF show them to be non-electrolytes^{9,10}.

Magnetic properties: The magnetic moment data of these complexes calculated from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities determined at room temperature are given in Table I. The μ_{eff} values reported for the complexes are slightly higher than the spin-only value of respective metal ions, indicating the spin-free octahedral environment around the metal ions¹¹⁻¹³.

* Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)					λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Metal	C	H	N	Cl		
[Mn(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	Dark red	232	10.68 (10.45)	50.24 (50.19)	3.01 (3.04)	10.58 (10.64)	13.44 (13.49)	45.44	6.01
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	Light black	216	10.98 (11.13)	49.98 (49.81)	2.98 (3.01)	10.54 (10.56)	13.34 (13.39)	30.36	4.12
[Ni(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	Brown red	205	11.2 (10.96)	50.0 (49.90)	3.12 (3.02)	10.62 (10.58)	13.24 (13.42)	19.36	3.17
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	Light green	240	11.74 (11.79)	49.46 (49.43)	3.10 (2.99)	10.52 (10.48)	13.24 (13.29)	22.21	1.75

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF 2-FURYLGLYOXAL-2-AMINOPYRIDINE AND ITS METAL CHELATES

2-Furylglyoxal-2-aminopyridine	Manganese chelate	Cobalt chelate	Nickel chelate	Copper chelate	Assignment
1 600s	1 510s	1 570m	1 590m	1 590m	C=N stretching
1 670m	1 640s	1 630m	1 620s	1 630s	C=O stretching
1 020s	1 020s	1 020w	1 020m	1 020m	C—O stretching
1 055s	—	—	—	—	(Pyridine ring) stretching
970m	—	—	—	—	
790m	—	—	—	—	—
	620m	590w	580s	580m	M—N stretching
	450s	440s	420m	420s	M—O stretching
	290m	270w	280s	280m	M—Cl stretching

s=Strong, m=medium, w=weak.

TABLE 3—EXPERIMENTAL TRANSITION ENERGIES, THEIR ASSIGNMENTS AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF Mn^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	${}^6A_{1g}$ ↓ 6E_g (4D)	${}^4A_{1g}$ ↓ 4E_g , ${}^4A_{1g}$ (4G)	${}^6A_{1g}$ ↓ ${}^4T_{1g}$ (4G)	B	C	Dq	F ₂	F ₄	β	λ	f	hν
[Mn(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	24 390	21 276	12 658	444.90	33.65	489.33	925.56	96.14	0.56	109.19	0.57	6.28
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	Band position (cm ⁻¹)		Assignment				10Dq (kcal mol ⁻¹)					
	12 987		${}^3B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3B_{1g} + {}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^3B_{1g}$				12.94					
	14 705		$(\nu_1 + \nu_2)$									
	20 833		${}^3A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^3B_{1g} (\nu_2)$									

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectra of 2-furylglyoxal-2-aminopyridine (Table 2) exhibit two strong bands at 1 600 (C=N) and 1 670 cm⁻¹ (C=O)¹⁴. These bands are found to be shifted to lower frequencies in the spectra of the corresponding metal complexes indicating the involvement of C=N and C=O groups in complexation^{15,16}. The position of the bands due to C—O—C at 1 020 cm⁻¹ remains unaltered even on complexation. The pyridine ring vibrations at about 1 055, 970 and 790 cm⁻¹ remain unaffected in the complexes as compared to ligand which suggest that pyridine nitrogen does not take part in coordination¹⁷. Three new bands appear in the spectra of the complexes at 580–620, 420–450 and 280 cm⁻¹ due to M—N, M—O and M—Cl stretching modes^{18,19}, respectively.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complex (Table 3), recorded in solution, show a number of bands (12 658, 21 276 and 24 390 cm⁻¹) of weak intensities. Since Mn^{II} has d⁵ electronic configuration, the same type of energy level diagram applies whether the metal ion is surrounded by tetrahedral or octahedral environment. Generally, four bands are observed and assigned to the transitions and energies in terms of Racah parameters²⁰,

$${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G), (17B+5C)$$

$${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g} ({}^4G), (10B+5C)$$

$${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g ({}^4D), (10B+5C)$$

$${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4P), (17B+7C)$$

Band corresponding to transition ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4P)$ was not observed due to instrumental limitations.

Since the energies of two transitions, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (4D) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}$ (4G) are independent of crystal field splitting (Dq) and depend only on B and C parameters^{21,22}. F_2 and F_4 can be calculated by using the values of Racah inter-electronic repulsion parameters B and C . On increasing delocalisation, β decreases and becomes less than one in the complex. Lower value of f and higher value of $h\lambda$ indicate the increase in covalent character on complexation.

Co^{II} complex (Table 4) shows three d-d bands in the region 11 627, 15 625 and 19 250 cm^{-1} which may be attributed to transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The values of transitions ν_1 , ν_2 , and ν_3 may be obtained by using König's equations²³. The ligand field parameters B and the ligand field splitting energy ($10Dq$) in the case of Co^{II} complex was calculated²⁴. Out of the four methods applicable in the case of Co^{II} complexes, the best fitting method is (c)²⁵ because of the ratio ν_3 (obs.)/ ν_1 (calcd.) is found to be 1.97 as required for octahedral Co^{II} complexes, and the calculated values of $10Dq$ is in good agreement to that determined by ν_3 (obs.) - ν_1 (calcd.). The values of $\beta_{3,5}$ of this complex is in the range 0.62-1.02 which clearly indicate the partial covalent character of the bond concerned.

The electronic spectrum of the complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (Table 4) is consistent with the octahedral geometry showing three d-d transition bands at 12 820, 20 833 and 27 027 cm^{-1} regions assignable to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. According to the weak field approximation the energy of the first band ν_1 corresponds to $10Dq$ while the second and third transitions are mixed by configuration interaction, and the energies

have been determined by

$$\nu_2, \nu_3 = \frac{1}{2}(15B + 30Dq) \pm [(15B - 10Dq)^2 + 12B \cdot 10Dq]^{1/2}.$$

The inter-electronic repulsion parameter B in case of Ni^{II} complexes has been obtained by different methods²⁶. Electronic spectral data were used to calculate the important ligand field parameters $10Dq$, $\beta_{3,5}$ and λ .

For d⁸ complexes with octahedral symmetry, the configuration interaction between $T_{1g}(P)$ and $T_{1g}(F)$ excited states lower the ratio ν_3/ν_1 from 1.80 (theoretical) to 1.63 (Ref. 27), which is in conformity with the experimental data supporting the distortion in octahedral geometry. The $\beta_{3,5}$ values show a trend of covalent bonding and CFSE value support the magnetic moment in the complex. The calculated data are found in good agreement with the observed values indicating small orbital contribution because of the spin-orbit coupling between the first excited state ${}^3T_{2g}$ and the ground state.

Three shoulder bands appear at 12 987, 14 705 and 20 833 cm^{-1} in the Cu^{II} complex (Table 3) which may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively. The E_g ground state is highly susceptible to Jahn-Teller configurational stability, due to which Cu^{II} ion in the complex shows distorted octahedral geometry²⁸. The energy difference gives the values of $10Dq$.

Antibacterial screening : All the metal chelates were tested for their antibacterial activity by disc-diffusion method²⁹ in DMF and found to be active against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *S. veridence* and *P. vulgaris*. The highest dilution of the test chelates which inhibited the visual growth of the test organisms was taken as the minimum inhibitory concentration (mic, $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) (Table 5).

TABLE 4—FOUND AND CALCULATED TRANSITION ENERGIES (cm^{-1}) AND VARIOUS LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF CO^{II} AND NI^{II} COMPLEXES

Methods of calculation	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	$B_{3,5}$	$10Dq$	$\delta\nu$	$\beta_{3,5}$	$\nu_3 - \nu_1$	ν_3/ν_1	$\delta\nu\%$			
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]													
Experimental—	11 627	15 625	19 250	—	—	—	—	—	—	—			
calculated													
(a)	Fitted	Fitted	24 207	701	9 998	—	0.72	—	—	—			
(b)	Fitted	29 625	Fitted	767	15 509	+14 000	0.78	—	—	47.25			
(c)	7 902	Fitted	Fitted	998	8 991	-3 725	1.02	7 723	1.97	47.18			
(d)	7 902	15 625	19 250	745	7 723	—	0.76	—	—	—			
[Ni(C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]													
	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	$B_{3,5}$	$\beta_{3,5}$	$\delta\nu$	$\frac{10Dq}{B}$	λ	ν_3/ν_1	ν_2/ν_1	f	$h\lambda$	CFSE kcal mol ⁻¹
Experimental—	12 820	20 833	27 027	—	—	—	—	—	1.68	2.11	1.44	—	43.95
calculated													
(a)	$10Dq$	Fitted	29 980	1 145	1.09	+2 953	11.19	90.01	—	—	—	0.75	—
(b)	$10Dq$	18 142	Fitted	330	0.82	-2 991	38.84	—	—	—	—	5.66	—
(c)	$10Dq$	19 022	28 843	627	0.60	+1 811	20.44	—	—	—	—	9.38	—
(d)	$10Dq$	18 636	27 519	513	0.49	-2 197	24.99	—	—	—	—	4.25	—

TABLE 5—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES* OF 2-FURVYLGLYOXAL-2-AMINOPYRIDINE AND ITS METAL CHELATES IN DMF AFTER 2 DAYS

Temp. = 37 ± 1°, inhibition zone diameters in mm.

Compd.	Organisms (Concn in µg cm ⁻²)														
	<i>E. Coli</i>			<i>S. Aureus</i>			<i>H. Subtilis</i>			<i>S. Versidene</i>			<i>P. Vulgaris</i>		
	25	100	500	25	100	500	25	100	500	25	100	500	25	100	500
C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃	—	3.5	7.0	—	—	5.0	—	5.0	11.0	—	8.5	12.0	—	6.0	7.0
[Mn(C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ Cl ₂]	—	4.0	12.0	—	4.0	10.0	—	—	8.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ Cl ₂]	—	—	—	—	4.0	10.0	—	—	6.0	—	—	2.0	—	—	4.0
[Ni(C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ Cl ₂]	—	—	—	—	—	4.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃) ₂ Cl ₂]	—	—	4.0	—	—	6.0	—	—	4.0	—	—	4.0	—	—	—

* DMF was used as a control and showed nil activity against above bacteria.

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